

ACCRETION DISK RADIATION OF THE QUANTUM-CORRECTED BLACK HOLE

Alloqulov Mirzabek

Ulugh Beg Astronomical Institute,

Astronomy str. 33, Tashkent, Uzbekistan

Abstract: In this work, the radiation properties of the accretion disk of the quantum-corrected black hole is studied. The equations of the flux of the electromagnetic radiation and the temperature of the disk were obtained. Moreover, the dependencies of the above mentioned quantities on black hole parameters were demonstrated in the appropriate figures.

A magnetically charged black hole solution is given by the following line element [1]:

$$ds^2 = -f(r)dt^2 + \frac{1}{f(r)}dr^2 + r^2(d\theta^2 + \sin^2\theta d\phi^2) \tag{1}$$

where

$$f(r) = \left(1 - \frac{2GM}{r} + \frac{\alpha G^2 M^2}{r^4}\right), \tag{2}$$

where M refers to the Arnowitt–Deser–Misner mass.

In this paper, we investigate the flux produced by an accretion disk of the quantum-corrected black hole. An accretion disk is a disk of gas and dust that orbits around a compact object such as a black hole or a neutron star. As the gas and dust in the disk fall towards the compact object, they heat up and emit radiation in a process known as accretion disk radiation. The accretion disk radiation for a quantum-corrected black hole belongs to an area of active research, as it has the potential to provide valuable insights into its properties. One can find the flux of the electromagnetic radiation using the following equation [2-4]

$$F(r) = -\frac{\dot{M}_0}{4\pi\sqrt{\gamma}} \frac{\Omega_{,r}}{(E-\Omega L)} \int_{r_{ISCO}}^r (E - \Omega L)L_{,r} dr \tag{3}$$

where γ is the determinant of the three-dimensional subspace with coordinates (t, r, ϕ) and given by $\sqrt{\gamma} = \sqrt{-g_{tt}g_{rr}g_{\phi\phi}}$. Note that flux of the electromagnetic radiation depends on \dot{M}_0 , which refers to as the disk mass accretion rate and remains unknown. We shall for simplicity choose $\dot{M}_0 = 1$. It is complicated to derive the analytical expression of the flux, and thus we resort it numerically; see Fig. 1.

Fig.1 Radial dependence of the flux of electromagnetic radiation of the disk on different values of α parameter.

As can be seen from the graphs that the flux of the electromagnetic radiation increases under the effect of the α parameter. Moreover, the flux of the black body radiation can be written as

$$F(r) = \sigma T^4 \quad (4)$$

with σ is the Stefan-Boltzmann constant. The radial dependence of the disk temperature is represented in Fig. 2. This graph depicts the dependence of the disk temperature and energy on the α parameter. One can see that the temperature and energy of the disk are increased with the increase in the α parameter.

Fig. 2 Top panel: The radial dependence of the temperature of the disk for different values of α parameter. Bottom panel: Temperature profile of the radial dependence α parameter is plotted in the bottom left panel, while in the bottom right panel temperature profile is plotted on the equatorial X – Y plane (i.e., we would mean the Cartesian coordinates by X and Y) in the form of density plot.

For being more informative, we demonstrate the temperature graph by “color map” in the bottom panel of the Fig. 2. One can now clearly notice the dark region inside the accretion disk’s inner edge, i.e., the red parts represent the regions that correspond to the disk’s maximum temperature.

References

- [1] J. Lewandowski, Y. Ma, J. Yang, and C. Zhang, Phys.Rev. Lett. 130, 101501 (2023).
- [2] I. D. Novikov and K. S. Thorne. Astrophysics and black holes. pages 343–550, 1973.
- [3] N. I. Shakura and R. A. Sunyaev. Black holes in binary systems. Observational appearance. Astron. Astrophys., 24:337–355, 1973.